

Developed cluster-based load-balanced protocol for wireless sensor networks based on energy-efficient clustering

Mohanad Sameer Jabbar¹, Samer Saeed Issa²

¹Department of Medical Instruments Techniques Engineering, Technical College of Engineering, Albayan University, Baghdad, Iraq

²Department of Computer Science, Al-Rafidain University College, Baghdad, Iraq

Article Info

Article history:

Received Jun 9, 2022

Revised Aug 30, 2022

Accepted Sep 29, 2022

Keywords:

Cluster-based routing

DCLP protocol

Energy-efficient protocol

LEACH protocol

WSN

ABSTRACT

One of the most pressing issues in wireless sensor networks (WSNs) is energy efficiency. Sensor nodes (SNs) are used by WSNs to gather and send data. The techniques of cluster-based hierarchical routing significantly considered for lowering WSN's energy consumption. Because SNs are battery-powered, face significant energy constraints, and face problems in an energy-efficient protocol designing. Clustering algorithms drastically reduce each SNs energy consumption. A low-energy adaptive clustering hierarchy (LEACH) considered promising for application-specifically protocol architecture for WSNs. To extend the network's lifetime, the SNs must save energy as much as feasible. The proposed developed cluster-based load-balanced protocol (DCLP) considers for the number of ideal cluster heads (CHs) and prevents nodes nearer base stations (BSs) from joining the cluster realization for accomplishing sufficient performances regarding the reduction of sensor consumed energy. The analysis and comparison in MATLAB to LEACH, a well-known cluster-based protocol, and its modified variant distributed energy efficient clustering (DEEC). The simulation results demonstrate that network performance, energy usage, and network longevity have all improved significantly. It also demonstrates that employing cluster-based routing protocols may successfully reduce sensor network energy consumption while increasing the quantity of network data transfer, hence achieving the goal of extending network lifetime.

This is an open access article under the [CC BY-SA](https://creativecommons.org/licenses/by-sa/4.0/) license.

Corresponding Author:

Mohanad Sameer Jabbar

Department of Medical Instruments Techniques Engineering, Technical College of Engineering

Albayan University

Baghdad, Iraq

Email: mohanad.s@albayan.edu.iq

1. INTRODUCTION

Information technology advancements are progressively influencing companies and community activities. This does appear to be preparing a manner for the industrial revolution 4.0 [1]. The embedding smart sensors within surroundings which connect via networks by wire or wirelessly in addition to internet protocols could allowing physical world to be incorporated into information systems. The internet of things (IoT) is widely used to describe such systems [2]. Wireless sensor networks (WSNs) have recently attracted widespread interest and application due to rapid growth of microelectrical-mechanical system (MEMS) technology and considerable advancement at wireless communication. The monitor of environments and habitat, controlling of industry, observation of battlefield [3], [4] monitoring of operational healthy [5], the diagnostic infrastructures and capabilities, besides other commercially employments [6] are just a few of the fields where WSNs are currently being used. One of the most WSNs fundamental purposes in recording

condition data detected through nodes intended for advance analyses to the sink, and there has been a lot of attention paid to building autonomic WSNs for industrial use.

Some protocols and techniques being used conventional wireless ad-hoc networks, such as the ad hoc on-demand distance vector (AODV), dynamically sourcing route (DSR), have been studied before. Suffusion WSNs applications, on the other hand, need more distinct properties [7]. The WSN is made up of distributing autonomous sensors that are able to physical situations monitoring in the region they are in, like pressure, sound, heat, and polluted air, and send the corresponding data to a central point via collaborative abilities. The data collected with such sensors is signals converting, which are then forwarded to a processing unit to expose a few characteristics about the region in which the sensor nodes (SNs) are located [8].

WSNs are made up of hundreds, if not thousands, of communicated nodes with restricted sensing, handling, besides computing susceptibility, as well as a restricted energy sources. They intended to perform good in place of many months, if not extended, depending on the application [9]. The nodes, on the other hand, are typically put in hostile and inaccessible environments, making it difficult or impossible to replenish energy neither replacing battery. As a result, part of nodes come to an energy ending, causing network division [10]. The energy efficiency of WSNs should be prioritized in order to extend their lifetime as much as feasible.

Clustering is the most common strategy for building energy-efficient designs, particularly for delivering energy-efficient and significantly enhanced sensor networks [11]. The regulatory clustering reduced the connections overhead significantly, reducing both the energy usage and SNs disruption [12]. Additionally, the defined node, which is the major duty of the cluster head (CH), collects sensor data, reducing the total data amount reaching main station along with bandwidth resources and limiting energies as shown in Figure 1. Some methods build clusters that are largely based on domestic traits, which aren't always the best. The necessity of producing load balance energy with operative clusters must be prioritized [13].

Figure 1. A WSN structure

In a variety of applications, WSNs have become more research-driven. Sensor networks have always required a lot of energy, according to scientists. Data aggregation is an effective energy-saving approach for extending the life of sensor networks. Because of their great reliability and adaptability, hierarchical cluster-based data aggregation techniques are commonly used among diverse approaches. However, there is an issue with imbalanced energy dissipation at clustering-based sensor networks [14].

The communication procedures in WSNs utilize the majority of the energy. The SNs perceive and collect data from their surroundings and send it independently to the sink. The energy resources available to SNs are limited. To overcome this issue, a number of energy-efficient routing techniques have been proposed. They are mostly grouped into two groups: flat routing protocols in addition hierarchical routing protocols [15].

Great efforts have been made in recent years to extend the lifetime of WSNs. The majority of these initiatives are focused on energy efficiency and balance. All known approaches may be classified into one of the following groups: i) controlling topology with medium access control (MAC) schedule: because loads of traffic are frequently unevenly distributed, it is a good idea to alter node density with various locations [16]. Furthermore, according to certain studies, various collision-free MAC scheduling techniques have been designed to reduce energy loss due to transmission collisions [17]; ii) energy-efficient routing methods, a slew of new protocols has lately developed. Protocols based on clustering, for example, are interesting

solutions because they facilitate data fusion plus have many desirable qualities like scalability and organization [18]; and iii) energy-balanced data propagation: this objective is to conserve energy by using energy-balanced data transmission systems. Because transmission accounts for a major portion of overall energy use, this technique is projected to save energy effectively, as illustrated in [19].

WSNs have been used in a variety of industries as the IoT has grown in popularity. The energy problem in WSNs has gotten a lot of attention lately, and a lot of specialists and academics have done a lot of research on it. Because SNs have a finite amount of energy, maximizing the network's lifetime has been a major subject in recent debate. Zhang and Chen [20] employed double stages for enhancing the clusters generation and a selection of CHs, which correlate to two processes, namely cluster formation and cluster operation. For WSNs with multilayer energy inhomogeneity, a novel clustering optimization approach was developed. Based on this technique, a wireless sensor network may balance network node energy consumption and extend the network's life cycle. The accuracy, energy consumption, and computational complexity of WSNs were also investigated [21]. For multi-hop WSNs have limiting energies, framework with an inverse non-uniform time synchronization had been established, and a synchronization of empty beacon energy-saving period system was created. The energy consumption and computing complexity were kept to a minimum in order to ensure synchronization precision. Given that available ambient energy is unpredictably variable and fluctuates over time, Aoudia *et al.* [22] provided a strategy with an implementation for achieving energy-neutral functioning on energies collecting wireless SNs. Such approach employs an adaptation of duty cycle by using management circuit of energy to deliver energy-neutral operation based on the availability of energy at surroundings in addition to node's current energy condition.

Several breakthroughs in recent years have aimed to increase the lifetime of the network using various strategies. The following are some of the most common methods currently being proposed. The low-energy adaptive clustering hierarchy (LEACH) considered as the most well-known distributed clustering-based routing algorithms [23]. It employs a method of equally distributing energy demands by spinning CHs at random. The CHs, on the other hand, don't chosen in a non-definitive manner, so they could spread unevenly. Additionally, data transferring of CHs straight to the sink; but who were further away from the sink will run out of energy sooner. A centralize routing protocol, denoted by low-energy adaptive clustering hierarchy centralized (LEACH-C), is suggested to overcome the issue that arose in LEACH. To build superior clusters, it employs a core algorithm. The sink in LEACH-C made cluster creation. Such CHs are chosen using the simulated annealing process [24].

Lindsey and Raghavendra [25] describes a protocol named power-efficient collecting in sensor information systems (PEGASIS). To make the transmission process easier, it creates a chain. It also specifies which nodes should send attached data for the sink. In a meanwhile, the nodes alternate transmitting data to lower average consumed energy resulting in increased lifetime of the network. Al-Mekhlafi *et al.* [26] reviews and discusses the algorithms that have been created to cope with the difficulties and systems that have inspired time synchronization via WSN in a wide sense. It is a thorough investigation that includes the transmission state instrument, places of interest, and the negative consequences of previous related work. Abderrahim *et al.* [27] proposes a multi-hop transmission technique for WSNs based on the Dijkstra algorithm WSN. Dijkstra is the basis for our suggested relay selection method. The major goal of the research is to define a novel transmission technique that improves on our prior work by more efficiently lowering power usage.

WSNs' energy-efficient cooperative communication across frequency-selective fading channels is investigated [28]. The closed-form bit error rate formulas are obtained for systems over frequency-selective fading channels. To fully explore the energy conservation potential of cooperative communications, the best transmission power allocation options and the partner node selection will be presented. Furthermore, chip-interleaving approaches in WSNs with flat fading channels have been shown to increase communication quality dramatically. As a result, the potential for energy savings in frequency selective decomposition of chip-interleaved transceivers in WSN is investigated in this work. This paper is briefly organized as follows: i) section 2 defines the configuration of WSN modelled and network's structure and their CHs within cluster-based protocols; ii) section 3 demonstrate the proposed cluster-based routing protocols while finally; and iii) section 4 highlights the results of the simulations and a comparison of SN lifetime with MATLAB could utilized for simulating LEACH, and its corresponding the distributed energy efficient clustering (DEEC), besides proposed algorithm the developed cluster-based load-balanced protocol (DCLP); and v) section 5 presents the conclusions.

2. METHOD

The WSN considers network made up of random SNs number that configure various clusters, separately with a CH node and many cluster members (CMs). According to its associated position, any CM

decides if can be belonged to cluster. In addition, each CM contain range of sensing at which any node may receive data then send it to an appropriate CH, which subsequently delivers it to sink node. Figure 2 depicts the network diagram utilized here [29].

If a SN be operational, it is often separated into two states: first is active when a working stage of a SN are the node has to transmit in addition to receive data, while second is sleep stage or idle listening if the node has no sending or receiving data. To save energy, all functionalities on the SN are switched off when it is in sleep mode. The SNs energy usage can be regarded zero within such state. The sensor network can be presented like a WSN model. The n number of SNs could be manually deployed in a complicated environment and put consistently and randomly in a $L*L$ square region [30]. The SNs set van be given by (1):

$$S = (s1, s2, \dots \dots sn) \quad (1)$$

the network's structure is depicted in Figure 1. There is a CH for each cluster, as well as CMs. The data is collected by each cluster member and forwarded to the CH. After that, all of CHs using role of the principle of aggregation and compression data will process such data before sending it to the sink node.

The fundamental network design and indeed the implementation of SNs being expected to be followed throughout the deployment of the nodes, such that a sink node which considers comparatively remote from the WSN can be connected physically, in the absence of energy usage regarding. These SNs as well as sink node considered stationary, and all SNs have the same beginning energy. Each SN in the network is given a unique identifier. The SNs able to change the power needed for transmission wirelessly depending on that situation. Finally, the node perceives the information in the surrounding environment and is constantly sending data. Despite the benefits of previous cluster-based routing protocols, there are very few challenges which have to be solved in order to reduce energy consumption and, as a result, enhance network lives. The following are the concerns that can be discovered.

First, CHs within cluster-based protocols can be considered in charge of collecting and aggregating data from their CMs before sending it to the designated destination [31]. As a result, the CHs' energy consumption is higher compared to CMs. Furthermore, if CHs send collected data with a long-distance transmission for base stations (BSs), it consumes a lot of energy and causes CHs to die prematurely [32]. Although many alternative clustering strategies have been presented to improve network performance, just limited researchers were focused on the rotation methodology. As illustrated in Figure 2, the rotation strategy, which is linked to cluster-based routing protocols, splits WSNs lifetime with many 'rounds.' At any round, the selection of new CHs for rotating the CH's role amongst some accessible nodes in accordance with the clustering. By evenly distributing the CH's responsibility among the nodes, load balancing improves and the network lifetime is extended. On the other hand, because CH rotation was carried out at each round over the complete network, the significant overhead is sustained each period of reassembling the clusters, which is inefficient in and of itself. To solve this challenge, realistic strategies for managing energy usage and extending the network lifetime must be identified.

Figure 2. Cluster-based model

Second, inequalities distributions of CH nodes inside a network plague cluster-based routing method for WSNs. This can result in greater energy waste [33], a disparity in energy consumption within clusters,

and a decrease in overall network performance. As a result, while building a cluster-based routing protocol, equitability from where distribution of the load is critical factor to consider.

Third, when CHs conduct network tasks in cluster-based protocols, they require more energy, which might cause nodes to die prematurely that causing failure of network. Selection an optimum CH may have a significant impact on the network's energy efficiency. A CH might be chosen based on the superiority of the nodes. This can be dependent on a variety of factors, including residual energy, node step, connection, and the distances between nodes.

3. EXISTING AND PROPOSED CLUSTER-BASED ROUTING PROTOCOLS

Differentiating and categorizing clustering techniques in WSNs may be accomplished in a variety of ways. The following are some of the most well-known cluster formation concepts and criteria that are used in CH selection. The main goal of the probabilistic selection clustering algorithm category is to increase the network's lifetime and scalability while lowering and equally distributing energy consumption. LEACH, energy-efficient hierarchical clustering (EEHC), hybrid energy-efficient distributed (HEED), with their expansions consider the most recognized protocols in this group. The probabilistic clustering techniques are discussed in further depth in the next section.

Heinzelman *et al.* [34] presented LEACH, the first well-known clustering technique that addressed the special demands of WSNs, such as prolonging WSN lifespan and reducing SN energy consumption. The LEACH protocol followed a type of single-hop that is hierarchical, probabilistic, and distributed. The received signal strength indicator (RSSI) is used by LEACH to create clusters. Furthermore, the CH nodes in the LEACH serve as BS routers. All data collection, in the mean of data fusion and aggregation, takes place inside the cluster.

LEACH considers also a distributing protocol in which nodes make autonomous judgments without relying on a centralized mechanism. The Opportunities of any node is equal of becoming CH, balancing each SN's energy usage every round. To determine if a node is a CH, it generates a random integer between 0 and 1 then compares it to threshold value $T(n)$, as shown in (2). CHs will be nodes having random number less than $T(n)$. To build a cluster, each chosen CH sends a greeting message to the non-CHs. This non-CH links CH which could be extended with a minimum communication energy [34]:

$$T(n) = \frac{p}{1 - p[r \bmod (\frac{1}{p})]} \text{ if } n \in G \quad (2)$$

where the provided node is n , p denotes the probability, current round denotes r , G denotes set of nodes which were didn't chosen as CHs in the former round, and the threshold denotes $T(n)$.

LEACH, in general, is a useful model of consumed energy since it gives an identical chance for the SNs to be nominated like CH. A SN who has been preferred to be CH can't become a CH again in the next round. Also, because LEACH use TDMA protocols, it avoids unwanted CH collisions.

Hameed *et al.* [35] propose another essential probabilistic clustering algorithm, EEHC. LEACH protocol's flaws, such as the one-hop random selection process, are addressed by the authors of this protocol. By repeating the clustering process at the level of CHs, EEHC protocol extends the network's multi-level construction, allowing for several layers of cluster hierarchy. There are two phases to the EEHC protocol: initial and extended. Initially, each SN sends a probability p hallo message to all neighbouring SNs containing communication range, offering them to join as CHs. This hallo message is acquired by nodes has a k hops coverage of a CH, either directly or indirectly. The nodes which get the message but are not CHs join the cluster nearest to them. The second step, referred to as the expanded stage, entails the creation of several layers inside the cluster structure. Between CHs and the BS, the protocol ensures multi-hop connection.

Younis and Fahmy [36] proposed HEED clustering. The authors refined the LEACH technique by selecting the CHs using two fundamental factors. The residual energy related for each node is a first factor, and the cost of intra-cluster communication with a function of cluster density or node degree is the second. Unlike the LEACH technique, the CH nodes in HEED are chosen in a methodical manner. Only the SNs with the most remaining energy are eligible to be nominated for CH nodes. Furthermore, double nodes have the same communication range possess a small likelihood of becoming CHs. If there is a comparison with LEACH and HEED protocols, the CH nodes in HEED are evenly distributed over the sensor field. HEED, on the other hand, the energy consumption is unbalanced as a result of more CHs being formed than expected, as well as large overheads due to several rounds.

One of the most difficult difficulties in WSN application design is managing energy usage in order to increase network performance. Despite the fact that various methods have been presented for addressing

such problem, assessing the performances of networks remains difficult. The SNs located far away for BS depend substantially on the efforts related to the group of intermediary nodes for transport corresponding data in a wide-range WSN scenarios. Alternatively, the nodes must send their data straight to the BS using high transmission power. Regardless method is used, the overall network's latency and power consumption are typically affected. The CH rotation strategy is a mechanism for maintaining cluster topology. It is essential for repairing, rotating, and reorganizing assembly of the cluster in order to prevent CH nodes from dying prematurely besides extending the lifetime of networks [37].

The architecture of the LEACH protocol is used by a large variety of routing systems. The network's life duration is broken into a series of periodic stationary rounds in such protocols. It could be demonstrated that using a static round time inside these protocols results in uneven load distribution. To improve load balance and guarantee effective energy use, the CH duty must be cycled across all nodes in the network. As a result, every set time, all network's nodes must be setting up with fresh CH selection procedure. However, because cluster-based protocols need consistent re-clustering in order to maintain a balanced consuming energy, reiterating the procedure of cluster over the completed network would raise network overhead then, as a result, reduce network operating time [38].

The proposed approach is based on realisation of HEED protocols. The HEED protocol's clustering phase could be tweaked to create it further effective of energy. This HEED protocol can break down into rounds, every one of them comprises two basic phases: setup and steady. Though, in the DCLP, these two phases are simply running within first round. DCLP can keep the clusters after the first round and rotate controlling among them in cluster itself with picking the node at high energy every round for reducing the regularity with which a BS sends out re-clustered messages. By reducing an overhead controlling message reciprocate throughout the re-clustering, this approach enhances energy efficiency.

4. SIMULATION RESULTS AND ANALYSIS

With a view to verify the success and efficiency of the proposed algorithm which is related to the SN lifetime, MATLAB could be utilized for simulating LEACH, and its corresponding DEEC, in addition to proposed algorithm DCLP. The benefits of SNs in WSN are then assessed in terms of longevity, data transmitted, and node subsistence condition. In this study, 200 SNs were dispersed at random in a 150*150 area, with the sink node fixed at (50, 50). The supplying energy was provided just the SNs were placed. Table 1 shows the particular parameter settings used during simulation.

Table 1. The parameters of our simulation

Parameters	Value	Symbol
Initial energy (J)	2.0	E initial
Number of iterations	4000	rmax
data packet Sizes (bits)	5000	Dz
Amplifier consumed energy Limits	0.0015	Emp pJ/bit/m4)
Parameters of amplifier energy consumption	12	pJ/bit/m2) Ef s
Eelec (nJ/bit)	50	
Routing protocols	3	LEACH, DEEC, DCLP

The WSN performance metrics that are applying for evaluating the algorithm's performances are as follows:

- Network lifetime, the time interval between the start of network operation and the death of the last live SN, as calculated by (3):

$$T_{lifetime} = t_{RDN} - t_{start} \quad (3)$$

where $t_{RND}=20$ the resistance-nodulation-division (RND), RND is the rounds number that a total SNs were died after, and t_{RND} represent the time for those SNs when dying.

- CHs number per round, each nodes number which immediately transmit information gathered from the choosing CMs directly for BS is adopted agreeing with threshold condition $T(s_i)$, k denotes to CHs optimal number, d_{toCH} represents the estimated distance between one sensor and CH, so that k may be calculated in various channel models as (4):

$$k = \frac{\sqrt{N}}{\sqrt{2\pi}} \frac{L}{d_{toCH}} \quad (4)$$

- c. Consumed energy in network, the consumed energy associated WSNs essentially consist of consumed circuit energy and the consumed power amplifying energy, with the last is leading. This energy can be calculated by (5) for various channel models
- d. Data transmitted amount, total volume of data that were transmitted via nodes (containing the CHs besides added nodes) within a WSN toward BS and may be determined by (6):

$$\begin{aligned} E_{round} &= k E_{cluster} \\ &= m (2N E_{elect} + N E_{DA} + K \epsilon_{fs} d^2_{toBS} + N \epsilon_{fs} d^2_{toCH}) \end{aligned} \quad (5)$$

$$data = data_{CH-BS} + data_{N-BS} \quad (6)$$

4.1. Network lifetime

Figure 3 compares LEACH, DEEC, and the DCLP considered in this study in terms of dead nodes. The slope of the DCLP algorithm's death node change curve was clearly lower than that of LEACH and DEEC. The SNs throughout a vast region began to die after the initial node death in the DCLP algorithm. After 2,500 cycles, the rate of node mortality was greatly lowered, and the network's lifespan was significantly increased.

Figure 3. Dead nodes number versus round numbers

This simulation compares the proposed DCLP protocol's network lifetime to that of various current protocols. Figure 3 depicts the dead nodes amount vs round numbers within WSNs. For DCLP protocols, nodes begin to die after 1,800, 1,900, and 2,500 rounds, accordingly. The nodes in the proposed DCLP, on the other hand, do not begin to die until 2,750 rounds. Furthermore, the DCLP protocol uses 3,400 rounds so that all nodes are dying, whereas for LEACH only 2,500 rounds. According to the findings, the DCLP increases network longevity by around 20% when compared to the other protocols.

4.2. Energy saving

Following the simulation round, Figure 4 shows total nodes number that are still active or alive. In comparison to its competitors, the DCLP extends the network lifetime. DCLP uses the least amount of energy, as can be shown. The LEACH protocol had an average lifetime of roughly 1,000 rounds, whereas the DEEC protocol had an average longevity of around 1,400 rounds. When comparing DEEC and DCLP, the average longevity was practically identical. This is due to the fact that DEEC employs a similar method that ignores leftover energy. As a result, by delaying the cluster process, the novel strategy of CH rotating job inside the cluster can be more energy saving.

Figure 4 depicts the variation in the number of active nodes for various protocols. DCLP clearly made an energy balancing usage across best clusters, but for other protocols, LEACH achieves poorly due to its CHs spinning randomly. DCLP uses an ideal cluster size approach to determine cluster size and picks CHs through evolutionary inter-clustering. As a result, it has a greater energy efficiency.

Figure 4. Live sensor numbers vs round numbers

4.3. Cluster heads number comparison

The CHs numbers vs the round numbers is depicted in Figure 5. After 1,000 rounds, maximum CHs numbers are reached, and after 3,150 rounds, CHs numbers became zero. While, in DEEC, maximum CHs numbers occur after 650 rounds, and after 2,500 rounds, CHs number became zero. The CHs numbers had been discovered for DCLP is 2,800 rounds, compared to 2,500 rounds for DEEC, that related to the attributable improvement that considered there is no participation of closer nodes to BS in establishment of clustering. Because DCLP considers the energy modification parameters while the CH selection, it is evident that it extends the network lifetime compared to DEEC and LEACH. Furthermore, during the 4,000 simulation rounds, the proposed DCLP protocol creates more CHs than others, reducing the consumed energy corresponding to WSN nodes. As a result, the suggested strategy is effective regards conserving energy besides prolonging the WSN's lifetime.

Figure 5. CHs number versus rounds number

The election CHs number every round is shown in Figure 5. In comparison to other routing protocols, the results suggest that LEACH has higher uncertainty. Because the criteria for randomized rotation of CHs are adjusted from LEACH, DEEC is somewhat superior in terms of CHs selection.

4.2. Setup messages overhead

Figure 6 illustrates a worldwide comparison of messages number used in the setup phase at 1,000 rounds for LEACH, DEEC, and DCLP. Due to the reduced re-cluster process, DCLP has the lowest rate of setup messages, resulting in less energy consumption and improved network performance. When compared to DEEC and LEACH, DCLP performs much better even though an increasing in nodes number.

Figure 6. Comparison of messages number used in the setup phase at 1,000 rounds

In WSNs, energy consumption is a major problem. Despite the fact that clusters-based protocols are among the best energy-efficient, and nonetheless experience from wasting energy throughout the processing of clusters. In these protocols, there is mandatory to network for going to fresh determination procedure each round to load balance CH election. This interactive clustering method consumes a lot of energy and time, especially during the setup phase of each cycle.

The same SNs numbers were put in the identical region. In comparison to previous LEACH, DEEC, and DCLP algorithms, the DCLP method used in this article may successfully extend the network's life cycle and considerably increase its stability. The network's data throughput was also boosted, and the sensor network's energy consumption was successfully reduced. The DCLP method could successfully enhance network stability and considerably boost data throughput even when varying SNs numbers could be placed within the equivalent cross-section of the network.

Furthermore, decisions were made based on a variety of variables, as well as certain components that were taken into account when designing the WSN. In terms of technologies, several feasible options have been made that will assist designers in selecting the most appropriate technology, as well as prospective performance levels. A self-selected CH gathers data seen from cluster's SNs, calculates, then relays the nodes conclusion. Similarly, even when the identical SNs number were organized with various network's cross-sections, DCLP algorithm outperformed the other algorithms within WSN. This is because, by adopting clustering, SNs might logically be passing in the sleep state through an idle listening time, lowering SN energy consumption and effectively enhancing SN performance.

The IoT is formerly having significant influence on people's lives. Its consisting of three parts: a sensing network, a transmitted network, in addition to an application network. With the sensing network, which makes up of wireless SNs, being the most essential. Its function is to detect, collect, analyze, and transmit data in the network's coverage area in a cooperative manner, sending the data to the users. As a result, the sensor network is critical to development and use IoTs. Because of the wireless sensor network's low cost, low consumed power, and fault tolerance when there is broking of some nodes, an entire network didn't be disabled.

5. CONCLUSION

This paper presents DCLP, a proposed developing methodology that provides a novel inter-cluster strategy. DCLP have an CH election rotating inside the similar CM to decrease the number of iterative clustering procedures. In each cycle, the node with the most energy receives first preference to become a CH. This innovative method tries to increase the network's lifetime while maintaining QoS. However, imbalance in CH node allocations across the network might result in nodes dying prematurely.

One of the most crucial challenges surrounding the usage of WSNs is energy efficiency. WSNs, are normally made up of huge SNs number which have been installed at random indoors or outdoors to monitor key parameters in their surroundings. Because the SNs are battery-powered, their power and processing capabilities are restricted, and they are subject to failure. When compared to existing routing protocols, cluster-based protocols can be thought as a best energy-efficient. The DCLP protocol's threshold incorporates four parameters: the nodes beginning energy, nodes residual energy, aggregating network energy, in addition to nodes regular energy. Furthermore, we assume that there is no participation of nodes closer to the BS in creation of cluster in order to save energy. Because sensor devices have a finite amount of energy, then the

greatest critical factor in any WSN protocol is the energy efficiency. However, security elements of routing protocols have received little attention for a long time.

REFERENCES

- [1] F. Farouk, R. Rizk, and F. W. Zaki, "Multi-level stable and energy-efficient clustering protocol in heterogeneous wireless sensor networks," *IET Wireless Sensor Systems*, vol. 4, no. 4, pp. 159–169, Dec. 2014, doi: 10.1049/iet-wss.2014.0051.
- [2] R. Ashween, B. Ramakrishnan, and M. M. Joe, "Energy efficient data gathering technique based on optimal mobile sink node selection for improved network life time in wireless sensor network (WSN)," *Wireless Personal Communications*, vol. 113, no. 4, pp. 2107–2126, Aug. 2020, doi: 10.1007/s11277-020-07309-y.
- [3] H. Cheng, Z. Su, N. Xiong, and Y. Xiao, "Energy-efficient node scheduling algorithms for wireless sensor networks using Markov Random Field model," *Information Sciences*, vol. 329, pp. 461–477, Feb. 2016, doi: 10.1016/j.ins.2015.09.039.
- [4] M. M. Kareem, M. Ismail, M. A. Altahrawi, N. Arsad, M. F. Mansor, and A. H. Ali, "Grid based clustering technique in wireless sensor network using hierarchical routing protocol," in *2018 IEEE 4th International Symposium on Telecommunication Technologies (ISTT)*, Nov. 2018, pp. 1–5, doi: 10.1109/ISTT.2018.8701720.
- [5] A. A. Hussien, S. W. Al-Shammari, and M. J. Marie, "Performance evaluation of wireless sensor networks using LEACH protocol," *Indonesian Journal of Electrical Engineering and Computer Science*, vol. 19, no. 1, pp. 395–402, 2020, doi: 10.11591/ijeecs.v19.i1.pp395-402.
- [6] T. M. Behera, U. C. Samal, and S. K. Mohapatra, "Energy-efficient modified LEACH protocol for IoT application," *IET Wireless Sensor Systems*, vol. 8, no. 5, pp. 223–228, Oct. 2018, doi: 10.1049/iet-wss.2017.0099.
- [7] S. H. Rhafif, A. H. Ali, R. K. Abdulnabi, and A. A. Abdulrazzaq, "Fiber optics based schemes modeling and simulation of QoS for Wi-Fi scenarios using OPNET modeler," *International Journal of Electrical and Computer Engineering (IJECE)*, vol. 10, no. 3, pp. 2569–2578, Jun. 2020, doi: 10.11591/ijece.v10i3.pp2569-2578.
- [8] D. Lin and Q. Wang, "An energy-efficient clustering algorithm combined game theory and dual-cluster-head mechanism for WSNs," *IEEE Access*, vol. 7, pp. 49894–49905, 2019, doi: 10.1109/ACCESS.2019.2911190.
- [9] R. Sinde, F. Begum, K. Njau, and S. Kajage, "Lifetime improved WSN using enhanced-LEACH and angle sector-based energy-aware TDMA scheduling," *Cogent Engineering*, vol. 7, no. 1, pp. 1–21, Jan. 2020, doi: 10.1080/23311916.2020.1795049.
- [10] Adnan H. Ali, A. D. Farhood, and M. K. Naji, "Analysis of a framework implementation of the transceiver performances for integrating optical technologies and wireless LAN based on OFDM-RoF," *International Journal of Electrical and Computer Engineering (IJECE)*, vol. 10, no. 4, pp. 4252–4260, Aug. 2020, doi: 10.11591/ijece.v10i4.pp4252-4260.
- [11] P. S. Basappa, S. Gangadhar, and T. C. Thanuja, "Energy-efficient data-aggregation for optimizing quality of service using mobile agents in wireless sensor network," *International Journal of Electrical and Computer Engineering (IJECE)*, vol. 12, no. 4, pp. 3891–3899, Aug. 2022, doi: 10.11591/ijece.v12i4.pp3891-3899.
- [12] M. A. Saad, Sameer A. S. Lafta, R. Kh. Al-Azzawi, A. H. Ali, S. Alani, M. M. Hashim, B. Hasan, "Total energy consumption analysis in wireless mobile ad hoc network with varying mobile nodes," *Indonesian Journal of Electrical Engineering and Computer Science*, vol. 20, no. 3, pp. 1397–1405, Dec. 2020, doi: 10.11591/ijeecs.v20.i3.pp1397-1405.
- [13] S. Chamanian, S. Baghaee, H. Ulsan, O. Zorlu, E. Uysal-Biyikoglu, and H. Kulah, "Implementation of energy-neutral operation on vibration energy harvesting WSN," *IEEE Sensors Journal*, vol. 19, no. 8, pp. 3092–3099, Apr. 2019, doi: 10.1109/JSEN.2019.2890902.
- [14] M. M. Kareem, S. A. S. Lafta, H. F. Hashim, R. K. Al-Azzawi, and A. H. Ali, "Analyzing the BER and optical fiber length performances in OFDM RoF links," *Indonesian Journal of Electrical Engineering and Computer Science*, vol. 23, no. 3, pp. 1501–1509, Sep. 2021, doi: 10.11591/ijeecs.v23.i3.pp1501-1509.
- [15] P. S. Mann and S. Singh, "Energy efficient clustering protocol based on improved metaheuristic in wireless sensor networks," *Journal of Network and Computer Applications*, vol. 83, pp. 40–52, Apr. 2017, doi: 10.1016/j.jnca.2017.01.031.
- [16] S. Seno, D. Abd Ali, and M. Mohammed, "Efficient routing protocol algorithm for wireless sensor networks," *Iraqi Journal for Computers and Informatics*, vol. 44, no. 1, pp. 11–17, 2018, doi: 10.25195/ijci.v44i1.67.
- [17] M. K. Abed, M. M. Kareem, R. K. Ibrahim, M. M. Hashim, S. Kurnaz, and A. H. Ali, "Secure medical image steganography method based on pixels variance value and eight neighbors," in *2021 International Conference on Advanced Computer Applications (ACA)*, Jul. 2021, pp. 199–205, doi: 10.1109/ACA52198.2021.9626807.
- [18] S. M. Azooz, J. H. Majeed, R. K. Ibrahim, and A. H. Ali, "Implementation of energy-efficient routing protocol within real time clustering wireless sensor networks," *Bulletin of Electrical Engineering and Informatics*, vol. 11, no. 4, pp. 2062–2070, 2022, doi: 10.11591/eei.v11i4.3916.
- [19] M. Kalla and A. Rawat, "Clustering algorithm for energy-efficient wireless sensor network," *Turkish Journal of Computer and Mathematics Education (TURCOMAT)*, vol. 12, no. 5, pp. 877–884, 2021, doi: 10.17762/turcomat.v12i5.1500.
- [20] J. Zhang and J. Chen, "An adaptive clustering algorithm for dynamic heterogeneous wireless sensor networks," *Wireless Networks*, vol. 25, no. 1, pp. 455–470, Jan. 2019, doi: 10.1007/s11276-017-1648-1.
- [21] S. Li, K. S. Kim, L. Zhang, X. Huan, and J. Smith, "Energy-efficient message bundling with delay and synchronization constraints in wireless sensor networks," *Sensors*, vol. 22, no. 14, pp. 1–15, Jul. 2022, doi: 10.3390/s22145276.
- [22] F. A. Aoudia, M. Gautier, and O. Berder, "RLMan: An energy manager based on reinforcement learning for energy harvesting wireless sensor networks," *IEEE Transactions on Green Communications and Networking*, vol. 2, no. 2, pp. 408–417, Jun. 2018, doi: 10.1109/TGCN.2018.2801725.
- [23] G. S. Arumugam and T. Ponnuchamy, "EE-LEACH: Development of energy-efficient LEACH Protocol for data gathering in WSN," *EURASIP Journal on Wireless Communications and Networking*, vol. 2015, no. 1, pp. 1–9, Dec. 2015, doi: 10.1186/s13638-015-0306-5.
- [24] C. Nakas, D. Kandris, and G. Visvardis, "Energy efficient routing in wireless sensor networks: A comprehensive survey," *Algorithms*, vol. 13, no. 3, pp. 1–65, Mar. 2020, doi: 10.3390/a13030072.
- [25] S. Lindsey and C. S. Raghavendra, "PEGASIS: Power-efficient gathering in sensor information systems," in *Proceedings, IEEE Aerospace Conference*, 2002, vol. 3, pp. 1125–1130, doi: 10.1109/AERO.2002.1035242.
- [26] Z. G. Al-Mekhlafi, Z. M. Hanapi, and A. M. S. Saleh, "Firefly-inspired time synchronization mechanism for self-organizing energy-efficient wireless sensor networks: A survey," *IEEE Access*, vol. 7, pp. 115229–115248, 2019, doi: 10.1109/ACCESS.2019.2935220.
- [27] M. Abderrahim, H. Hakim, H. Boujemaa, and F. Touati, "A clustering routing based on Dijkstra algorithm for WSNS," in *2019 19th International Conference on Sciences and Techniques of Automatic Control and Computer Engineering (STA)*, Mar. 2019,

- pp. 605–610. doi: 10.1109/STA.2019.8717279.
- [28] J. Tian, S. Berber, and G. Rowe, "Energy efficient cooperation with chip-interleaved transceivers in WSNS over frequency-selective fading channels," *Wireless Personal Communications*, vol. 95, no. 4, pp. 3933–3953, Aug. 2017, doi: 10.1007/s11277-017-4033-6.
- [29] M. A. Kafi, Y. Challal, D. Djenouri, M. Doudou, A. Bouabdallah, and N. Badache, "A study of wireless sensor networks for urban traffic monitoring: Applications and architectures," *Procedia Computer Science*, vol. 19, pp. 617–626, 2013, doi: 10.1016/j.procs.2013.06.082.
- [30] V. Katiyar, N. Chand, and S. Soni, "Clustering algorithms for heterogeneous wireless sensor network: A survey," *International Journal of applied Engineering research*, vol. 1, no. 2, pp. 273–287, 2010, [Online]. Available: <https://citeseerx.ist.psu.edu/viewdoc/download?doi=10.1.1.207.360&rep=rep1&type=pdf>
- [31] S. A. S. Lafta, M. M. Abdulkareem, R. K. Ibrahim, M. M. Kareem, and A. H. Ali, "Quality of service performances of video and voice transmission in universal mobile telecommunications system network based on OPNET," *Bulletin of Electrical Engineering and Informatics*, vol. 10, no. 6, pp. 3202–3210, Dec. 2021, doi: 10.11591/eei.v10i6.3139.
- [32] M. Gheisari *et al.*, "A survey on clustering algorithms in wireless sensor networks: Challenges, research, and trends," in *2020 International Computer Symposium (ICS)*, Dec. 2020, pp. 294–299. doi: 10.1109/ICS51289.2020.00065.
- [33] F. Faniyan and M. K. Rafsanjani, "Cluster-based routing protocols in wireless sensor networks: A survey based on methodology," *Journal of Network and Computer Applications*, vol. 142, pp. 111–142, Sep. 2019, doi: 10.1016/j.jnca.2019.04.021.
- [34] W. R. Heinzelman, A. Chandrakasan, and H. Balakrishnan, "Energy-efficient communication protocol for wireless microsensor networks," in *Proceedings of the 33rd Annual Hawaii International Conference on System Sciences*, 2000, pp. 1–10. doi: 10.1109/HICSS.2000.926982.
- [35] B. H. Hameed, A. Y. Taher, R. K. Ibrahim, A. H. Ali, and Y. A. Hussein, "Based on mesh sensor network: design and implementation of security monitoring system with Bluetooth technology," *Indonesian Journal of Electrical Engineering and Computer Science*, vol. 26, no. 3, pp. 1781–1790, Jun. 2022, doi: 10.11591/ijeecs.v26.i3.pp1781-1790.
- [36] O. Younis and S. Fahmy, "HEED: A hybrid, energy-efficient, distributed clustering approach for ad hoc sensor networks," *IEEE Transactions on Mobile Computing*, vol. 3, no. 4, pp. 366–379, Oct. 2004, doi: 10.1109/TMC.2004.41.
- [37] B. Salih Hassen, S. Abdul-Sattar Lafta, H. M. Noman, Adnan H. Ali, "Analyzing the Performances of WSNs Routing Protocols in Grid- Based Clustering", *International Journal on Advanced Science, Engineering and Information Technology (IJASEIT)*, vol. 9, no. 4, pp. 1211-1216, 2019.
- [38] X. Huan, K. S. Kim, S. Lee, E. G. Lim, and A. Marshall, "A beaconless asymmetric energy-efficient time synchronization scheme for resource-constrained multi-hop wireless sensor networks," *IEEE Transactions on Communications*, vol. 68, no. 3, pp. 1716–1730, Mar. 2020, doi: 10.1109/TCOMM.2019.2960344.

BIOGRAPHIES OF AUTHORS

Mohanad Sameer Jabbar is Assistant professor at Al-Bayan University, Baghdad, Iraq in Technical College of Engineering, Department of Medical Instruments Techniques Engineering where he has been a faculty member since 2021. I'm graduated with a B.Sc. degree in mathematics since from Mustansiriyah University, Baghdad, Iraq and an M.Sc. in computer since from university of Singhania-Jhunjhunu, India in 2010. and Ph.D in computer since specialized in network and communication from university of Singhania-Jhunjhunu, India in 2013. Our research interest in the area of network, communication, and network security. He can be contacted at email: mohanad.s@albayan.edu.iq.

Samer Saeed Issa is Assistant Professor at Al-Rafidain University College, Baghdad, Iraq, where he has been a faculty member since 2010. I 'am graduated with a BsC. Degree in computer science from University of Technology–Baghdad, Iraq, in 1999, and an M.Sc. in Data Security from University of Technology–Baghdad, Iraq, in 2002, and Ph.D from Iraqi Commission for Computers and Informatics/Informatics institute for post graduate Studies-Baghdad in 2006. Our research interests in the area of network and data security. He can be contacted at email: samer.saeed.elc@ruc.edu.iq.